

RELATIONSHIP OF ADOLESCENT CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *This is dedicated to the problem between parents and children. Philosophical and medical support for the relationship between parents and children in the family will be considered, and the characteristics of the relationship between parents and children in the modern family.*

Today's family is one of the most important social institutions to observe the belief in their consideration, thereby forming an active moral attitude towards the family and considering the problems.

Keywords: *Puberty, morphological structures, reproductive system, hormonal changes, school and physiological changes.*

ОТНОШЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ-ПОДРОСТКОВ В СЕМЬЕ

Аннотация. *Посвящена проблеме взаимоотношений родителей и детей. Будет рассмотрено философско-медицинское обеспечение взаимоотношений родителей и детей в семье, а также особенности взаимоотношений родителей и детей в современной семье.*

Сегодняшняя семья является одним из важнейших социальных институтов, при соблюдении которых необходимо учитывать веру, тем самым формируя активное нравственное отношение к семье и рассмотрению ее проблем.

Ключевые слова: *половое созревание, морфологические структуры, репродуктивная система, гормональные изменения, школьные и физиологические изменения.*

Relationships with parents and families: how they change in adolescence. Pre-teen and teenage relationships with parents and families change during adolescence, but pre-teens and teenagers need parent and family support as much as they did when they were younger. When your child was young, your role was to nurture and guide them. Now you might be finding that your relationship with your child is becoming more equal. You remain a source of care, emotional support, security and safety for your child, as well as practical and financial help. Your child still loves you and wants you to be involved in their life – even though their attitude or behaviour might sometimes send a different message. Most young people and their families have ups and downs during these years, but things usually improve by late adolescence as children become more mature. And family relationships tend to stay strong right through. Why pre-teens and teenagers need parents and families. Adolescence can be a difficult time. Your child is going through rapid physical changes as well as emotional ups and downs. Young people aren't always sure where they fit, and they're still trying to work it out. Adolescence can also be a time when peer influences cause stress. During this time, your family is a secure emotional base where your child feels loved and accepted, no matter what's going on in the rest of their life. Your family can build and support your child's confidence, resilience, optimism and identity. When your family sets

rules, boundaries and standards of behaviour and builds strong relationships, you give your child a sense of consistency, predictability, safety and belonging. And believe it or not, your life experiences and knowledge can be useful to your child – they just might not always want you to know it! Supportive and close family relationships protect your child from risky behaviour like alcohol and other drug use and mental health problems like depression. Your support and interest in what your child is doing at school can boost their desire to do well academically too.¹

Strong family relationships go a long way towards helping your child grow into a well-adjusted, considerate and caring adult. Building positive family relationships with teenagers: The ordinary, everyday things that families do together build, strengthen and nurture relationships with teenagers. These tips might help you and your family. Show love and appreciation, Show your child how much you love and appreciate them. This can be as simple as saying ‘I love you’ each night when they go to bed or giving them a high five. Have family meals

Regular family meals are a great chance for everyone to chat about their day or about interesting stuff that’s going on or coming up. ²If you encourage everyone to have a say, no-one will feel they’re being put on the spot to talk. Also, many families find that meals are more enjoyable when the TV isn’t on and mobile phones and tablets are switched off! Go on family outings.

Try setting aside time for fun family outings – you could all take turns choosing activities.

A family day trip or weekend away can also build togetherness. Our article on teenagers and free time has more ideas for things you can do as a family. Make one-on-one time. One-on-one time with your child gives you the chance to stay connected and enjoy each other’s company.

It can also be a chance to share thoughts and feelings. This might be as simple as going for a walk together, watching a movie, or telling your child a story. Or you might find a regular hobby to do together, like cooking or yoga. Celebrate your child’s accomplishments

Celebrating your child’s accomplishments, sharing their disappointments, and supporting their hobbies sends the message that your child’s interests are important to you. You can often do this in simple ways – for example, by showing up to watch your child play sport or giving them a lift to extracurricular activities. Make family traditions. Family traditions, routines and rituals can help you and your child set aside regular dates and special times. For example, you might have a movie night together, a favourite meal or cooking session on a particular night, a family games afternoon or an evening walk together. Agree on household responsibilities

Agreed household responsibilities can give your child the sense that they’re making an important contribution to family life. These could be things like chores, shopping or helping older or younger members of the family. It helps to give your child some say in which responsibilities they take on. Set family rules

Agreed rules, limits and consequences can give your child a sense of security, structure and predictability. They help your child know what standards apply in your family and what will happen if they push the boundaries. When your child is involved in making your family rules,

¹ Muuss, R. (1996) *Theories of Adolescence*. New York: McGraw Hill. Sixth Edition.

² Howe, D., Brandon, M., Hinings, D. and Schofield (1999). *Attachment Theory, Child Maltreatment and Family Support. A Practice and Assessment Model*. Palgrave: Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire and New York.

they're more likely to see them as fair and stick to them. Negotiating rules together can also help you to reduce and manage conflict with your child. Have family meetings

Family meetings can help to solve problems. They give everyone a chance to be heard and be part of working out a solution. Get extra support

If you feel that your family isn't connecting, it can help to look for a family counsellor or other family support service.

Role of Family in Adolescent Development. Developmental theories view adolescence as a period of growth in which identity formation is addressed ¹. This can be interpreted to mean that the role of family is lessening or that family have only a limited role in the lives of young people at this time. Research shows, however, that ongoing positive family connections are protective factors against a range of health risk behaviours. Although the nature of relationships is changing, the continuity of family connections and a secure emotional base is crucial for the positive development of young people.

The need for a secure-base. Adolescents are moving towards becoming independent physically, emotionally and cognitively, and yet they are still growing.

Young people still require stability in a home environment, and a secure emotional base from which to explore and experience the world. This also provides them with somewhere to come back to for reassurance, support and unconditional love in tough times. A young person benefits from expectations of respect, consideration and reciprocity in family relationships. ³They still benefit from 'trying out' thoughts, feelings and behaviours within the family environment, and from observing and experiencing relationships within families. There will still be times when they fall, and will benefit from understanding and support to pick themselves back up.

Changing role of parents. A parent's relationship and caring role with a young person continues to be important, although the relationship will need to be flexible to adapt to the teenager's changing needs. At this time, there will need to be a gradual change from a more authoritative approach, to a more collaborative approach.

Parents have to face the (sometimes hard) reality that their child is no longer a child, is becoming independent and is no longer within their control. They may feel distressed as they perceive that the young person won't listen to them, or does the opposite of what they may suggest.

They may have to watch their young person disregard the things they thought they taught them were important, such as ways to look after their health, or their future goals (as the parent envisaged it).

⁴Parents have to learn to 'let go', not of the relationship, but of their dreams for the young person, and their authority over the young people, so that they may allow a young person to develop their own dreams and greater self-responsibility.

Guidance and boundaries. Guidance and boundaries are still important, however the quality of the relationship, and collaboration rather than 'obedience', becomes increasingly important if a relationship is to survive and be maintained.

³ Fuller, A. (2000) *Raising Real People: Creating a Resilient Family*. Melbourne: ACER

⁴ Daniel, B., Wassell, S. & Gilligan, R. (1999) *Child Development for Child Care and Protection Workers*. UK: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

Joint discussions about rules/options, compromise and flexibility for win/win solutions are important. Warmth and understanding are important, rather than judgmental comments or telling a young person what to do.

Consequences need to be age-appropriate, and not punitive (see: Setting Boundaries).

Monitoring of a young person's whereabouts is still important to the extent possible, especially when adolescents are still young.⁵ Parental supervision, and access to a parent for support and assistance, are crucial protective factors in young people's health⁵. It can be helpful for caregivers to consider the age at which they think their young person will be an adult, and to think about and look forward to, how they would like their relationship with their child to be then.

This may lead them to think about and nurture the relationship shift needed between now and then (see: Building our Relationship).

Role modelling. A family and its members continue to provide valuable role models for a range of behaviours, including effective communication, relationship skills, and socially acceptable behaviours. The ways in which conflict and disagreements are negotiated within the family are important blueprints for dealing with issues in other arenas.

Appropriate boundary setting also gives young people clear guidelines as to what is acceptable and what is not; skills which can be generalised to a wider context. Young people benefit from modelling about how to have constructive disagreements while maintaining a continuing positive relationship.⁶ They still benefit from experiencing an effective model for relating to others and negotiating life and the world. When families are not providing a secure-base. When there is no family contact, efforts need to be made to reconnect young people with appropriate family members. Alternatively, other significant adults are needed who may provide the elements and safety net for emotional development. The developmental needs of a young person, as outlined in this help sheet, must be met somehow to optimise health outcomes. Some families seem to work against a young person developing their own sense of self-worth, self-identity and their capacity for independent decision-making and emotion-regulation.

Understanding and working with the family dynamics may assist the family's capacity to provide a young person with a secure-base on which to continue to develop. Caregivers and other family members and particularly the young person will benefit from being told more about how the family may be operating in a way which is detrimental to a young person's development. It can be useful to try to build a more positive picture of the young person in the family (see: Family Dynamics). Encourage carers to gain support in dealing with issues relating to their adolescent, either through family and friends or other support groups. The help sheets in the Parent section of this website may be useful. There are times when contact with some or all family members is detrimental and alternative 'families' need to be engaged.

The educational process of a teenager is mainly related to stress. In such periods, it should be remembered that the body needs more than ever proteins, B vitamins, pantothenic acid, vitamins

⁵ Blum, R. & Rinehart, P. (1998) [Reducing the Risk: Connections that Make a Difference in the Lives of Youths](#).

⁶ Muuss, R. (1996) *Theories of Adolescence*. New York: McGraw Hill. Sixth Edition.

A, E, because each of these elements is involved in the production of pituitary and adrenal hormones. The ability of our teenage body to withstand stress largely depends on these hormones.

A healthy lifestyle for teenagers is not just a word. It not only helps a person to feel full, but is also a kind of choice of life position. Boys and girls, already almost adults, decide for themselves what is good and what to avoid. If parents believe that they can control their child's every move, they are deeply mistaken. Therefore, it is important that the principles of a healthy lifestyle are consciously chosen by the teenager himself, and then these rules take root, apply and bring benefits.

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